

WHY GST FOR INDIA-NEED AND CHALLENGES FOR THE SUCCESS OF GST IN INDIA

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Abstract:

GST will be significant step towards a comprehensive indirect tax reform in the country since 1947. The basic idea of GST is to replace existing tax levies like VAT, excise duty, service tax and sales tax by levying a comprehensive tax on the manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services in the country. GST is expected to build a transparent and corruption-free tax administration. GST will divide the tax burden equitably between manufacturing and services. Goods and Services tax is planned at creating single and uniform market that will benefit both corporate and the economy.

This paper presents the Need for GST and the Challenges for success of GST in India.

Keywords: Goods and Service Tax, GST, VAT, Input credit

1. Introduction:

Tax policy as a major role on Indian economy through its impact on efficiency and equity. A good tax system should keep in view issues of income distribution and also generate tax revenues to support government expenditure on public services and infrastructure development. The structure of Value Added Tax (VAT), recognized as GST has been one of the major reform in indirect tax system.

GST will help in having single tax system by introducing integrated Goods and Service Tax (GST) which will finally help in developing a common national market. GST will increase the consumption, encourage exports, increase the employment opportunities and will give a boost to the economy.

The current state of Indian economy claims fiscal consolidation and reduction in fiscal deficit. A report by CRISIL states that GST is the country's best to achieve fiscal consolidation. The Country's attempt to build and create a common market with a unified indirect tax structure (GST) received a boost on Tuesday, the 10 November 2009. The Empowered Committee of State Finance Ministers introduced the First Discussion Paper on the GST. The implementation of Goods and Services Tax (GST), which is scheduled to be rolled out from April 1, 2016.

1. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study has been carried out towards achieving the following objectives:

- i. To understand the concept of Goods and Services tax;
- ii. To know the needs for Implementation of GST;
- iii. To Examine the challenges for Success of GST in India;
- iv. To provide information for future research works on Goods and Services tax.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research paper is an attempt of exploratory research, which is based on the secondary data sourced from magazines, journals, articles and media reports.

According to the requirements of the objectives of the study which are of fact findings the research design used for the study is of descriptive type. Keeping in view of the set objectives, this research design was adopted to have greater accuracy and in depth analysis of the research study.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Jaiprakash, (2014) studies "Indirect tax reforms in India and a way ahead for GST", and found that GST will ensure the greater uniformity in the tax rates throughout the country and will end the cascading effect which is

yet to be implemented. GST would offer broaden tax base, GST has to be introduced as it is favorable and economy will have steady growth with only mild inflation.

Syed Mohd Ali Taqvi, Amit Kumar Srivastava, Ravindra Kumar Srivastava, (2013) studied “Challenges and Opportunities of Goods and Service Tax (GST) in India and found that the GST is aimed at creating a single, unified market that will benefit both corporate and the economy. GST is likely to improve tax collections and boost India’s economic development by breaking tax barriers between states and integrating India through a uniform tax rate.

4. WHAT IS GST?

GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and service at a national level. GST is a value added tax (VAT) and is supposed to subsume most of the indirect taxes existing at the level of state and federal governments. GST is a valued added tax on goods and services that is paid by the final consumer while the retailer will be taking credit of the tax he has paid while buying goods for retailing.

5. KEY FEATURES OF THE GOODS AND SERVICES TAX

- **Two components:** There are two components of GST one levied by the centre (Central GST) and other levied by the states (State GST), rates for which would be prescribed appropriately, reflecting revenue considerations and acceptability of central and state.
- The central GST and the state GST would be applicable to all **transactions of goods and services** made for a consideration except the exempted goods and services, goods which are outside the purview of GST.
- A two-rate structure – a **lower rate** for necessary items and goods of basic importance and a **standard rate** for goods in general. There will be a special rate for precious metals and a list of exempted items.
- The GST will be levied on **import of goods and service** into the country.
- The administration of the **central GST to the centre and for state GST to the states** would be given. This would imply a reduction in unhealthy competition among the centre and the states over tax revenue that was prevalent earlier and an increase in harmonious functioning between centre and state.

6. NEED FOR GST:

Need for GST is the current state of Indian Economy requires a tax structure which emanate fiscal consolidation and reduce fiscal deficit. A recent report by CRISIL states that GST is the country’s best tax levy to achieve fiscal consolidation.

N1: As various transactions take the character of sales as well as services, thus there is complication in determining the **Nature of transactions** which will further help in shortening the transaction process.

N2: Current law has resulted in consequential **Number of Issues** relating to interpretation or various provisions and also in categorizing the products and the nature of services.

N3: For Inter-State transactions, Innovative model of Integrated GST (IGST) is been adopted by GST. Maintenance of uninterrupted ITC (Input Tax Credit) chain on inters- a State transaction is the major advantage of IGST model. India needs a comprehensive levy and collection of tax on both goods and services at the same rate with the **Benefit of Input Credit**.

N4: Reduced transaction process leads to a simple tax structure which will bring greater consent, thus **Increasing Number of tax payers** and in turn tax revenues of Government.

N5: GST will ensure **Competitive Pricing**. Tax paid by final consumer will come down in maximum cases. Lower prices will help in boosting consumption.

N6: GST will result in fall in cost of production in the domestic market. Indian Goods and Services will be more prices competitive in foreign markets. GST will ensure in **Boost to Exports** of our country.

7. GST-Challenges for success in India:

Goods and Service Tax will be the biggest reform in the indirect tax system of India. There are changes required in the existing tax structure in India but there are many challenges for the successful implementation of GST in India.

- GST can be implemented only by taking the acceptance of GST bill passed by all the respective state governments in state assemblies so as to bring majority.
- Central Government has full majority in the lok sabha and therefore GST bill would be passed in the lower house of the parliament. But Central Government as to ensure the safe passage of GST bill in Rajya Sabha as it is not a strut to pass a bill in upper house of the parliament.
- As tax credits are provided, the revenue would not be the same as current system. Hence, through RNR (Revenue Neutral Rate) government as to ensure that its revenue remains the same. The comparison of VAT Rate / RNR of peer Countries with that of India is as under:

Japan	5%
South Africa	14%
Germany	16%
China	17%
U.K.	17.5%
Russia	18%
India	27% (Proposed)

Higher RNR / GST rate would hamper the prospect of successful implementation of GST in India.

Source:<http://taxguru.in/goods-and-service-tax/challenges-success-goods-service-tax-gst-India>.

- The success of GST would greatly depend on the robust IT backbone. Currently GSTN (Goods and Service Tax Network) is functioning, GSTN has to develop GST portal which include technology support for registration, return filing, tax payments, IGST settlement, MIS etc.
- Empowered committee and Central government should ensure that lowering of threshold limit should not be a “taxing” burden on small businessmen in the country.
- For effective implementation of GST, tax administration staff both at central and state level would require to be trained properly in terms of concept, legislation and procedure of GST.
- States will be allowed to levy an additional 1% non-vatable tax on inter-state supply of goods for the initial 2 years or more. The purpose of additional levy is to compensate the states for loss of revenue while moving to GST.

8. CONCLUSION

GST is a single and transparent tax which will widen the tax base, improve tax compliance, removal of cascading and improve competitiveness. In GST, all indirect taxes such as excise duty, central sales tax and value added tax etc. will be subsumed as a single tax levy.

The need for GST is as it will reduce the cost of locally manufactured goods and services which will increase the competitiveness of Indian goods and services in the international market and will boost Indian exports. GST will ensure competitive pricing this will lower pricing which will help in increasing consumption.

India has to overcome all the challenges and successfully implement GST. As many countries are benefited from moving to a GST regime.

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